

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES,
SRINIVAS NAGAR, MUKKA, SURATHKAL,**

VALUE ADDED COURSE

ON

Personality Development

DEPARTMENT OF MENTAL HEALTH NURSING

Name of the course:Personality Development

Aim of the Course:

The aim of the course is to help students acquire an in-depth knowledge in factors influencing personality development, theories of personality development, personality traits, and personality disorders and further acquire skill in knowing one's own personality, understand others in their surroundings and bring positive change in life.

Objectives of the Course

On completion of the module, the student will be able to

1. describe how personality develops
2. define various stages of personality development
3. describe basic personality traits and personality types
4. analyze how personality affects career choices
5. describe methods for changing personality
6. enumerate personality disorders
7. demonstrate skills in identifying personality disorders
8. utilize knowledge in knowing self and others and improve relationship with others
9. provide care to patients with personality disorders by emphasizing on respecting individual culture and spiritual needs

Duration:

Theory: 30 hours

Practical: 20 hours

Evaluation :

Assessment methods:

- Test paper (Objective test, short answers and case scenario and questions) - 30 marks
- Assessment of assignments/skills - 20 mark

The examination will be conducted by the Institute of Nursing Sciences affiliated to Srinivas University

Criteria for eligibility to appear for University Exam

- i.80% attendance in theory
- ii.100% attendance in practical

Criteria for pass

In order to pass a candidate should obtain at least 50% marks aggregate including internal Assessment and marks obtained from college examination

Award of Certificate/Diploma

Certificate will be awarded by the Institute of Nursing Sciences affiliated to Srinivas University.

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Abhisree K V

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Adithya A

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Airin Willy

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Aiswarya Krishnan K

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Aiswarya Radhakrishnan C M

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to

01/08/2022.

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Ajanya A

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Akhina Gopi G

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Akshaya P P

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Aleena Anto

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Rajita'.

Course Coordinator

Dean

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Aleena Raj V K

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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Aleena S

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Aleena Susan Mathew

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Amrutha Anil

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Anamika K

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Ancy Mol S

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Aneena Joseph

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Angel Mary Thomas

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Anjali P S

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Anjana Venu

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Anna Grace

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Annmaria Mathew

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Aparna K

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Arya K

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Arya Ravindran

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Ashnitha Jose

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Asritha P

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Aswani A

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Aswani O K

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Aswathi Sandeep P

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Athira K V

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Athul P P

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Avanthika Mahesh

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Ayisha Afra

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Blessy K B

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Chaithra

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Chandini A

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Cindrella Ben Mathew

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Disna Paul

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Fairusa Jabeen

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Feba Jayamon

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Fesna T A

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Hariyat V S

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Jismaya P

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Jobin Johny

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Jothis Thomas

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Kavya T V

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Keerthana Narayanan K V

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Keran Sara Sabu

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Kezia Sara Thomas

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Rajita'.

Course Coordinator

Dean

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Krishnapriya K V

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Lakshmi Santhosh

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Liyamol Jacob

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Liyana Sherin

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Meenakshi R

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Megha Vijayan

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Melba Martin

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Murshida Nesrin E N

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Nandana Pavithran

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Nandana S

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Nandana Sathyan

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Nivedya Raju C

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Niya Sandriya Panagadan

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Parvathee Krishna U S

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Praise Anna Babu

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Priya M

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Raisa K

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Rawan

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Reshna P V

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Rose Mariya Raju

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Roshna B L

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Rudra Priya V S

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Safa Fathima B S

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sandhya V N

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sandra Binoy

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sandra Joseph

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sangeetha Renji

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Saniya Nazeer

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sanjana T V

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sankeerth K

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Rajita'.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Shana Sherin P T

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Rajita'.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Shiva Nanda

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Shruthi V

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sneha Animon

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sneha Chandrasekhar M

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sneha K

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sona Ebby

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Rajita'.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sona Saji

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sree Lakshmi Das K

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Suhana Shereef K

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Surya A B

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Thanvi

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Varsha Varghese

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Yadhukrishna K

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES MUKKA, MANGALORE

COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Ishwarya

I Year BSc Nursing has successfully completed 30 hours of value added course on "Personality Development" from 01/03/2022 to 01/08/2022.

Course Coordinator

Dean